

**Bridging
Research and
Standards:
Success stories from
HSbooster.eu**

December 2024

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Disclaimer

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Acknowledgements

The HSbooster.eu team would like to extend its gratitude to the experts and research project representatives who participated in HSbooster.eu, sharing their time, expertise, and insights. Their collaboration and dedication have been instrumental in achieving the success stories highlighted in this booklet.

1. Introduction

[HSbooster.eu](https://hsbooster.eu) is a Horizon Europe-funded initiative aimed at integrating standardisation into the workflows of EU-funded Research and Innovation (R&I) projects. Launched in April 2022, this pilot project offered tailored support to align R&I outputs with relevant standards, enabling the valorisation and sometimes improving the market readiness of research results. As of November 2024, HSbooster.eu has supported over 300 projects and delivered more than 250 standardisation services, ranging from personalised consultancies to the facilitation of deep-dive workshops and contributions to CEN Workshop Agreements (CWAs).

The project has followed a phased methodology that incorporates continuous feedback from participants, ensuring that services evolved based on the practical needs of projects. This adaptive approach has enabled HSbooster.eu to provide actionable guidance and tools, including a chatbot, a [Standards Orientation Tool \(SOT\)](#), to help projects navigate standardisation pathways and a *standards catalogue*, currently in preparation. Several webinars have also been organised to provide sector-specific guidance and a full [Training Academy](#) is available for both projects and individuals interested in learning more about standards in practice

This report highlights the tangible outcomes of HSbooster.eu, presenting some success stories that demonstrate the impact of the initiative across diverse thematic areas such as digital innovation, sustainability, advanced technologies, health, and other emerging fields. Through these examples, the report outlines the broader implications of integrating standardisation into R&I, drawing lessons to inform future policy frameworks and support programmes. A complete set of recommendations has been published by the project and is available for download [here](#)

By fostering collaboration between projects, standardisation bodies, and technical experts, HSbooster.eu has contributed to reducing the gap between research outputs and their application in real-world contexts.

The findings and lessons presented here underline the value of structured standardisation support in enhancing the impact of R&I projects. At the same time, they emphasise the need for continued investment in initiatives that enable alignment between research, standards, and market demands.

2. Overview of selected success stories

The success stories presented in this report reflect the varied contributions made by R&I projects supported by HSbooster.eu. These projects illustrate how tailored standardisation support has enabled them to overcome technical challenges, align with relevant standards, and achieve societal and market impact.

A few projects were selected based on their tangible outcomes, innovative approaches, and alignment with HSbooster.eu's overarching objectives. This includes contributions to developing new frameworks, engaging with technical bodies, and advancing sustainability and innovation in emerging fields. The categorisation below groups these projects by their primary contributions and highlights their impact.

Defining new frameworks and methodologies

These projects developed frameworks, terminologies, or methodologies that address specific gaps, providing a foundation for future standardisation efforts:

- **IDERHA** developed an interoperability framework for the European Health Data Space by clustering with other health-focused projects. This framework supports harmonised data sharing practices across Europe, aligning with EU health policy goals.
- **Nanomecommons** is preparing a CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA) to establish a unified terminology and metadata framework for materials science, enhancing interdisciplinary collaboration.
- **SHINTO** defined terminology for self-healing materials and initiated a working draft for an ISO standard in soft robotics, contributing to foundational definitions for this emerging field.
- **TRIANGLE** contributed to ITU-T Study Group 12 with a draft recommendation for 5G testbed environments, addressing key pre-standardisation needs.

Engaging with standardisation bodies to influence existing standards

These projects actively engaged with standardisation bodies, contributing to ongoing discussions or adapting existing standards to align with project outcomes:

- **HELIOS** liaised with multiple technical committees to influence standards in battery management systems (BMS) and privacy management frameworks, including ISO 27701.
- **SELFY** presented results to ISO/TC 204, advancing discussions on connected vehicles and intelligent transport systems.
- **BEST4Hy**: was advised to contribute to sustainable fuel cell recycling by engaging with IEC/TC 105, IEC TC111 and ISO/TC 197, addressing gaps in end-of-life management of fuel cells.

- **SINGLE:** was advised to engage with ISO/TC 197 and CEN/CLC/JTC 6, as well as propose new standards related to ammonia as part of the hydrogen value chain.
- **COGITO:** with HSBooster support, identified and prioritised standardisation proposals to present at various standardisation committees active in the construction industry

Integrating sustainability into standardisation

These projects contributed to aligning innovative practices with sustainability goals, promoting circularity and resource efficiency:

- **Ashcycle** supported the development of standards for reducing the waste generation from the incineration of municipal solid waste (MSW), biomass, sewage sludge, or combinations of them by developing new utilization possibilities and by engaging with CEN technical committees, promoting resource-efficient materials.
- **Houseful** focused on circularity in construction, working with CEN/TC 350 to align methodologies with sustainable housing practices.
- **NetworkNature** promoted urban sustainability by aligning biodiversity and natural systems initiatives with standards developed by CEN/TC 465.
- **AVANT:** Addressed sustainability challenges in veterinary practices in antimicrobial use.

Advancing innovation in emerging technologies

These projects addressed the unique challenges of emerging technological fields, laying the groundwork for future developments:

- **ROMSOC** aligned an acoustic device model with standards, contributing to advancements in digital twins and mathematical modelling.
- **SNS-OPS** developed a standards tracker for 6G technologies, providing a comprehensive resource to guide pre-standardisation efforts.
- **INFINITECH and FAME** advanced blockchain-related de facto standardisation activities, showcasing the application of distributed ledger technologies in various sectors.
- **HoloZcan:** contributed to standardisation in holographic microscopy by aligning its innovations with relevant technical committees.
- **H2Value:** refined its internal processes by mapping where standardisation could enhance risk management and operational planning and received tailored recommendations to strengthen its ability to contribute to evolving standards, supported by targeted training on building capacity among city officials and stakeholders to navigate the complexities of hydrogen value chain.

3. Main Lessons learned

Over its almost 3 years of operation, HSbooster.eu has identified key insights into successfully supporting research and innovation projects in navigating the complexities of standardisation. These lessons highlight approaches that have proven effective in maximising impact and fostering alignment with standards.

1. Flexible support models are essential

The diversity of project needs, technological domains, and maturity levels requires a flexible and tailored approach to consultancy. Adapting services to the specific context of each project ensures relevance and enhances the likelihood of successful outcomes.

2. Early assessment and guidance create strong foundations

Standardisation readiness assessments are vital for identifying project needs and tailoring support. Early-stage guidance enables projects to establish clear roadmaps, understand the relevant standards landscape, and plan engagement with standardisation bodies effectively.

3. Practical tools streamline standardisation efforts

The availability of tools to assess readiness and visualise relevant standards helps projects better understand the standardisation landscape. These tools provide insights to orient project strategies effectively, enabling teams to focus on relevant pathways and opportunities for engagement.

4. Collaboration enhances knowledge sharing and innovation

Facilitating collaboration between projects with similar challenges or thematic focus fosters knowledge sharing and innovation. Group settings such as workshops or consultations allow for cross-pollination of ideas and more efficient problem-solving across domains.

5. Ongoing support is critical for standardisation success

Standardisation is an iterative process that often requires ongoing guidance. Continuous support throughout a project's lifecycle helps address unforeseen challenges, ensures alignment with evolving standards, and sustains engagement with relevant bodies.

Selected success stories in detail

Discover more at

<https://www.hsbooster.eu/success-stories>

Keywords:

#standardisation, #circulareconomy,
#construction, #building, #housing, #design,
#environment, #assessment

Building a Circular Future: Empowering the Construction Industry through Standardisation.

Background

The building construction sector is currently in the midst of a transformation towards a more sustainable and circular approach. Traditional construction methods often generate significant waste and use inefficiency in resource utilisation. However, a wave of innovative research projects has emerged to revolutionise the industry by introducing novel solutions that embrace circularity and promote sustainable practices within building construction. By rethinking conventional approaches, these projects are paving the way for a more environmentally conscious and resource-efficient future in the sector.

The Challenges

The building construction sector has long faced obstacles in adopting circular practices due to the absence of standardised approaches. The lack of clear regulations and standardisation frameworks hinders the effective implementation of circularity strategies. Recognising these challenges, the HOUSEFUL project embarked on a mission to align their efforts with emerging standardisation practices to enhance the adoption and impact of their circularity tool.

Keywords:

#standardisation, #circulareconomy,
#construction, #building, #housing, #design,
#environment, #assessment

Building a Circular Future: Empowering the Construction Industry through Standardisation.

HOUSEFUL

The project

HOUSEFUL is an Innovation Action funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and Innovation programme under grant agreement N°776708. It focuses on driving circularity in the building construction sector. With the development of their Circularity Tool as a key exploitable result, HOUSEFUL aims to transform the industry by enabling practitioners to make informed decisions during the design and construction phases.

The Circularity Tool provides a web-based platform for assessing and evaluating the degree of circularity in new building or renovation projects, offering a clear and understandable evaluation of circularity. By leveraging this tool, practitioners can gain insights into the circularity of their projects, optimise resource use, reduce waste, and embrace sustainable building practices. With the HOUSEFUL's Circularity Tool, the building construction sector can embark on a path towards a more circular and sustainable future.

HOUSEFUL REPRESENTATIVE

**Arnau
González**

Head of European and Innovation Projects at Aiguasol

"In a climate-neutral Europe, buildings not only will be part of the energy system infrastructure but also circular in relation to their materials and resilient to climate risks."

The Project Standardisation Needs

To ensure the widespread adoption and impact of the Circularity Tool, HOUSEFUL recognised the importance of aligning their methodology with ongoing standardisation efforts. They sought to collaborate with relevant Technical Committees working on Building Circularity standards, aiming to ensure the tool's compatibility with emerging practices. By integrating their methodology into recognised standards, HOUSEFUL aimed to establish a consistent and recognised framework for evaluating circularity in building projects.

Keywords:

#standardisation, #circulareconomy,
#construction, #building, #housing, #design,
#environment, #assessment

Building a Circular Future: Empowering the Construction Industry through Standardisation.

The HSbooster.eu Expert

Carlos Del Castillo, the expert assigned by HSbooster.eu, played a pivotal role in supporting HOUSEFUL's standardisation endeavours. He is a Project, Sustainability and Advocacy Manager at the European Convention for Constructional Steelwork (ECCS). He actively contributes to the work of Technical Committees and Working Groups at the European Committee for Standardisation (CEN), including CEN TC 350 and CEN TC 135. With expertise in circular economy and sustainable construction, Carlos plays a crucial role in shaping standards and guidelines related to smart cities, circular economy in buildings, and design for circularity in the construction sector.

The HSbooster.eu Consultancy service

The assigned HSbooster.eu expert recognised the value of HOUSEFUL's circularity assessment methodology. He provided valuable insights and guidance to the project team, facilitating their engagement with relevant standardisation activities and committees. In particular the following activities were performed:

- HOUSEFUL underwent an evaluation of its standardisation readiness. This involved assessing the project's current use of standards and identifying opportunities for further standardisation integration.
- The expert provided detailed information on the standardisation landscape, including relevant Technical Committees, Working Groups, and National Standard Bodies. He highlighted ongoing initiatives related to circularity in the construction sector, such as the work being done in CEN TC 350/SC1/WG1.
- The project also received recommendations on accessing key standards
- Additionally, the expert advised on standardisation strategies and engagement approaches. He recommended participating in introductory meetings with relevant TC/SC Chairs and Secretariats to gain an overview of standards work programs. He also encouraged the project team to present their work to relevant Technical Committees, Working Groups, and General Assemblies to enhance visibility and collaboration.

THE HSBOOSTER.EU EXPERT

**Carlos
Del Castillo Bonet**

Sustainability, Project and Advocacy Manager at ECCS

"It was a pleasure to support HOUSEFUL. The project outcomes as well as the future consortium involvement in standardisation activities will be key in circularity assessment."

Keywords:

#standardisation, #circulareconomy,
#construction, #building, #housing, #design,
#environment, #assessment

Building a Circular Future: Empowering the Construction Industry through Standardisation.

Benefits & Impact

The support provided by Carlos and HSbooster.eu has brought benefits for HOUSEFUL. The project gained a deeper understanding of standardisation practices and opportunities in the field of circularity in the construction sector. By aligning with ongoing standardisation activities and engaging with relevant committees, HOUSEFUL has the opportunity to position itself as a valuable contributor to the development of circular economy principles in building construction. The integration of standards and standardisation practices enhances the project's credibility and relevance, enabling the methodology developed by HOUSEFUL to become a potential reference for future standards in the field of circularity assessment. This recognition and alignment with standards will not only enhance the impact of the project but also contribute to the broader adoption of circular practices in the industry.

Useful material

- [Best Practice Book](#)
- [Interactive sharing Platform for circular services](#)

Future Plans

Based on the insights and recommendations provided by Carlos, HOUSEFUL has a clear strategy for the future. The project is considering to apply for delegation on CEN TC 350, ensuring active participation in the development of standards related to environmental performance and circular economy in the construction sector.

HOUSEFUL plans to establish contact with relevant committees and mirror committees to foster collaboration and knowledge sharing. The project team will engage in discussions and expert meetings to contribute to the ongoing development of methodologies and frameworks for circularity assessment and performance evaluation.

Moving forward, HOUSEFUL remains committed to flexibility, openness, and alignment with EU strategies and regulations. The project will explore emerging approaches, such as digital passports, to further enhance circularity, sustainability, and the overall impact of their work.

Keywords:

#standardisation, #circulareconomy,
#construction, #building, #IoT, #AI, #BIM,
#CloudComputing, #assessment

Materialising the Digitalisation Benefits for the Construction Industry through Standardisation.

Background

Digitalisation for lean construction is a stepping stone to achieve the industrialisation of the construction sector. The construction industry has traditionally been known for its inefficiencies, complex processes, and high costs. Optimise project management, minimise waste, and improve productivity in the construction process through digitalisation is not only possible, but also needed. This process involves leveraging cutting-edge technologies, such as, Building Information Modelling (BIM), IoT, Cloud Computing and Artificial Intelligence. This set of technologies can enable real-time data collection from various sensors and devices, providing valuable insights for decision-making, and analyse vast amounts of data, leading to better resource allocation and reduced waste.

The Challenges

The digitalisation journey in the construction industry is not without its challenges. One significant hurdle is the lack of commonly agreed standards and low interoperability among the vast amount of collected data. This poses a major drawback to enterprises' digital transformation efforts, even for large construction companies equipped with state-of-the-art digital reality capture tools. Without standardised frameworks and seamless data integration, the potential benefits of digitalisation remain fragmented, hindering the industry's ability to fully harness the power of emerging technologies. As the industry strives to embrace Digital Twins and leverage IoT, Cloud Computing, and AI, addressing these interoperability issues becomes a pressing necessity for ushering in a new era of efficiency and productivity in construction projects.

Keywords:

#standardisation, #circulareconomy,
#construction, #building, #IoT, #AI, #BIM,
#CloudComputing, #assessment

Materialising the Digitalisation Benefits for the Construction Industry through Standardisation.

The project

COGITO introduces a real-time digital twin of a construction project, using methods to ensure interoperability among the different components and technologies constituting the Digital Twin ecosystem, following the lean construction principles. COGITO is a project funded under the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme. It aims to materialise the digitalisation benefits for the construction industry by harmonising Digital Twins with the Building Information Model concept and to establish a digital Construction 4.0 tool-box. COGITO targets a semantic and pragmatic alignment between novel data capture techniques and delivery of value-adding end-user services leveraging the power of near-real-time data for the timely detection of health and safety hazards to humans, construction quality defects as well as a constantly up-to-date workflow management in order to minimise construction project time/cost overruns and alleviate workplace accidents.

COGITO REPRESENTATIVE

**Raúl
García-Castro**

COGITO's Standardisation Task Leader

"Standardisation is a cornerstone in COGITO and thanks to the HSbooster.eu services we have had the opportunity of strengthening it."

The Project Standardisation Needs

COGITO project focuses on advancing standardisation in construction, data modelling, and linked open data. It plans to engage with key industry bodies to gather feedback and garner interest in its standardisation initiatives. Consortium partners have been active in standardisation activities and contributed to the EUOS Landscape of Digital Twin Standards. They also submitted a use case for the upcoming ISO/IEC 30172 standardisation effort. COGITO sought HSbooster.eu open call support to elevate its standardisation efforts, aiming to submit results to at least four standards.

Keywords:

#standardisation, #circulareconomy,
#construction, #building, #IoT, #AI, #BIM,
#CloudComputing, #assessment

Materialising the Digitalisation Benefits for the Construction Industry through Standardisation.

The HSbooster.eu Expert

René Lindner is a PhD candidate at Tecnun - University of Navarra, focusing on the integration of standardisation in research projects related to smart and resilient cities. René holds a diploma in industrial engineering from the Technical University of Berlin, with expertise in technology and innovation management, project management, marketing, and multimedia systems. In his professional career, René Lindner serves as a Senior Project Manager at DIN German Institute for Standardisation. He also leads the Smart City Standards Forum at DIN and DKE. René actively participates in EU research projects related to city resilience, climate change, and smart cities, taking charge of standardisation activities. Notably, he took on the standardisation activities in the Horizon2020 projects **ARCH** and **SMR**, among others.

The HSbooster.eu Consultancy service

The COGITO partners and the HSbooster.eu expert focused on harnessing the results coming from the development of a Digital Twin model for the construction phase over a set of meetings, when the standardisation activities and potential contributions were discussed. COGITO partners are already participating in 14 standardization activities at different levels. René supported COGITO in identifying possible contributions to standardisation in more detail. Throughout the initial meeting different paths for contributing to standardisation were discussed. Furthermore, the expert provided initial insights on further standardisation options, best practices of conducting standardisation activities in research projects as well as other related national standardisation initiatives. The expert received a table with a set of standardisation proposals that COGITO could deliver to the different standards committees or other working groups, where its partners are involved. René gave advice on the standardisation activities for the project's remaining duration. The project aimed to promote its results to several standardisation bodies and contribute to four standards. The expert advised the project when to conduct the standardisation workshop to present the COGITO's potential contributions to standardisation properly.

THE HSBOOSTER.EU EXPERT

René Lindner

Leiter Smart City Standards Forum at DIN

"For projects like COGITO, multiple paths to standardization are possible – but only by understanding the benefits of each can high impact be achieved."

Keywords:

#standardisation, #circulareconomy,
#construction, #building, #IoT, #AI, #BIM,
#CloudComputing, #assessment

Materialising the Digitalisation Benefits for the Construction Industry through Standardisation.

Benefits & Impact

COGITO benefits from the expert's consultancy in various ways. The expert provided insights into standardisation options, including CWAs and Liaisons, enhancing COGITO's understanding of contribution routes.

Best practices shared by the expert aided COGITO's standardisation planning. Suggestions to engage with new standardisation bodies expanded COGITO's reach. This expert's information is vital for COGITO's standardisation activities, aiding workshop development and report preparation.

The expert's consultancy greatly contributes to COGITO's success in standardisation, facilitating engagement with standardisation bodies, promoting outcomes, and making impactful contributions to the construction industry's standardisation community.

Useful material

- [Report on COGITO standardisation outcomes promotion efforts](#)

Future Plans

Based on the insights and recommendations provided by René, COGITO has defined a clear strategy for the future.

The project highly appreciated the support received from the HSbooster.eu expert, finding it valuable and timely, leading to more options for standardisation activities and the preparation of the related report for the European Commission.

COGITO plans to establish contact with relevant technical committees where the project partners were not previously involved to foster collaboration and knowledge sharing.

The project team will engage in discussions and expert meetings to contribute to the ongoing development of methodologies and solutions for advanced Digital Twins in the construction industry.

Keywords:

#standardisation, #urbanmobility,
#electromobility, #environmentalfingerprint,
#energystorage, #IoT, #battery

High-performance modular battery packs for sustainable urban electromobility

Background

With the growing concern over climate change and air pollution, cities around the world are increasingly adopting sustainable mobility solutions to reduce their carbon footprint. Electromobility, particularly electric vehicles, has emerged as a promising alternative to traditional internal combustion engine vehicles. Sustainable urban electromobility aims to replace conventional fossil fuel-powered vehicles with electric vehicles to promote cleaner and greener transportation in cities. The roadmaps and targets for the optimisation of Li-ion technologies and for the development of new chemistries, such as Li-S, Li-air, or solid-state batteries, are then defined in the Integrated SET-Plan (Action 7) High-performance battery technology is critical for urban electromobility, where EVs are required to have sufficient power, range, and fast charging capabilities to meet the demands of daily urban commuting.

The Challenges

Universally accepted standards for battery pack modules and interfaces can increase the interoperability and unlock the flexibility of integrating batteries into different electric vehicle platforms. Standardisation is crucial to ensure seamless compatibility and facilitate easy replacement or upgrading of battery modules. These standards should address factors such as thermal management, fast charging, and overall system reliability. Adherence to regulatory requirements is also critical for the market acceptance. Harmonising the standards with existing regulations and guidelines helps ensure that these batteries meet safety, environmental, and quality criteria. Standardised communication protocols between battery packs and electric vehicles are vital as well for seamless integration and efficient operation. Common communication protocols enable effective battery management and enhance overall vehicle performance. Additionally, designing battery packs with modular and scalable features requires standardisation in size, form factor, and connectivity. Standardised interfaces and components allow easy upgrading and replacement, promoting circular economy principles.

Keywords:

#standardisation, #urbanmobility,
#electromobility, #environmentalfingerprint,
#energystorage, #IoT, #battery

High-performance modular battery packs for sustainable urban electromobility

The project

HELIOS aims at developing and integrating innovative materials, designs, technologies and processes to create a new concept of smart, modular and scalable battery pack for a wide range of electric vehicles used in urban electromobility services, from mid-size full-electric vehicles to electric buses, with improved performance, energy density, safety and Levelized Cost of Storage (LCoS). This project aims at i) developing new technologies in the field of advanced materials, Li-ion batteries, thermal management, power electronics, sensors and ICTs, which combined allow to create a new concept of standardised, modular and scalable hybrid Li-ion battery pack for urban electromobility applications; ranging from mid-size vehicles to electric buses, with improved performance, autonomy, safety and LCoS, and minimum carbon footprint; ii) creating new eco-designs and processes, which facilitate its reuse in second life applications and further recycling at its EoL, contributing to a circular and integrated supply chain in the EU for the fabrication of battery packs, as well as effective and sustainable models for urban electromobility; iii) demonstrating the effectiveness of the solution in relevant use cases for urban electromobility, such as EV cars e-Bus fleets.

The Project Standardisation Needs

The EU Electric Vehicle (EV) industry faces aggressive global competition, and each car manufacturer invests significantly in developing their own solutions, leading to a lack of standardisation in the industry. HELIOS focuses on defining scenarios, procedures, and certification standards for validating its solution in car-sharing and e-bus applications. The project addresses standardisation of battery management system (BMS) technologies to maximise compatibility, safety, and quality for large EV battery packs. HELIOS deals with the lack of standards and data-sharing for the residual value of battery capacity, proposing standardised methodologies and protocols to extract useful data from EV battery cells. Overall, the project aims to foster standardisation in the automotive industry, enabling efficient and sustainable electromobility services while promoting compatibility and safety across various applications.

Keywords:

#standardisation, #urbanmobility,
#electromobility, #environmentalfingerprint,
#energystorage, #IoT, #battery

High-performance modular battery packs for sustainable urban electromobility

The HSbooster.eu Expert

Leila C.W. Muchanga-Hvelplund is a chartered engineer, a chartered quality professional and a Lean practitioner with 15 years of combined experience in transportation, including digital technology and passenger experience (e.g., road and rail). Leila currently works as an Independent Expert at CINEA (The European Climate, Infrastructure, and Environment Executive Agency) and is the Founder & CEO of ASI.Gov ApS in Denmark. As a Transportation Research Assistant at the University of Birmingham, Leila conducted a systematic literature review to support the development of a traffic fatality reduction strategy in India. During the tenure at Accenture, Leila served as an offshore Project Manager, successfully managing the design, procurement, and implementation of an IT platform cloud solution for the EMEA, Americas, and Asia. At Costain in the UK, Leila held the position of Research and Development Manager, introducing a new in-house tool for bridge movement. As a quality professional, both at project and programme level, she performed with quality management practices (e.g., ISO standards, knowledge share, training materials, lectures) as Leila also worked as a Technical Architect at Ericsson in the Netherlands and a Digital Television Interactive Engineer at UPC in Ireland.

The HSbooster.eu Consultancy service

To support the project's standardisation activities, the consultancy service provided several recommendations:

- Standardisation readiness: HELIOS and the expert assessed the preparedness for standardisation and aligned HELIOS' objectives with relevant standards.
- Standards and standardisation mapping landscape: The expert helped identify relevant standards and technical committees related to HELIOS' work, ensuring adherence to established norms.
- Standardisation strategy and engagement: Engaging with key stakeholders in standardisation bodies, like ISO, IEC, IEEE, CEN, and CENELEC, can help the project influence and contribute to relevant standards.
- Standards deliverables: The experts recommended that HELIOS consider submitting proposals for new work items in existing technical committees to contribute to the standardisation process.
- Training material: The expert suggested that HELIOS partners participate in HSbooster.eu webinars and national-level education programmes to enhance the project's understanding of standardisation.
- The consultancy service also pointed out specific resources, such as ISO standards, technical manuals, and EU legislation, related to wireless communication protocols, data privacy (GDPR). The service highlighted the importance of data-driven BMS, providing information on collecting specific data formats.
- Furthermore, the consultancy service suggested looking into ISO 27701 for managing privacy information and recommended participating in existing standardisation projects related to Battery and BMS to accelerate the standard development process within the project's tight timeframe.

THE HSBOOSTER.EU EXPERT

Leila C.W. Muchanga-Hvelplund

Founder and CEO of ASI.Gov ApS

Success and structure: These things provide.

Keywords:

#standardisation, #urbanmobility,
#electromobility, #environmentalfingerprint,
#energystorage, #IoT, #battery

High-performance modular battery packs for sustainable urban electromobility

Benefits & Impact

Leila's support through HSbooster.eu has brought several benefits to HELIOS. Thanks to her expertise, the project now possesses a deeper understanding of standardisation practices and opportunities within the electromobility and transport domain. By aligning with ongoing standardisation activities and actively engaging with relevant committees, HELIOS has the unique opportunity to establish itself as a key contributor to the advancement of urban mobility solutions.

The successful integration of standards and standardisation practices not only bolsters the project's credibility and relevance but also positions the innovative methodologies developed by HELIOS as potential benchmarks for future standards. This recognition and alignment with industry standards not only enhance the impact of the project but also contribute significantly to the broader adoption of accepted standards within the sector. Leila's support and the collaboration with HSbooster.eu have played a pivotal role in strengthening HELIOS's position as a leader in sustainable urban electrification and fostering a more standardised and interconnected electromobility landscape.

Future Plans

Based on the insights and recommendations provided by Leila, HELIOS has a clear strategy for the future. HELIOS will actively liaise with Technical Committees (TC), Subcommittees (SC), and Working Groups (WG) that are pertinent to the project's objectives. By establishing connections with these bodies, HELIOS can contribute to the development of standards in the field of electrification and transport. HELIOS will also consider obtaining trial memberships in national mirror committees related to its research domain. This will provide the project with valuable insights into ongoing standardisation activities and opportunities for collaboration. HELIOS will prioritise engagement with standardisation bodies at both the system level and the battery level. This multi-level approach will ensure comprehensive standardisation coverage. Moving forward, HELIOS remains committed to flexibility, openness, and alignment with EU strategies and regulations.

Keywords:

#standardisation, #selfhealingmaterial, #softrobotics, #flexibleelectronics, #ISO, #CEN, #ecodesign, #greentransition

SHINTO: Mapping Standards in the Realm of Self-healing Properties.

Background

Soft robotics is an emerging field of robotics that focuses on designing and building robots with soft and flexible materials. Unlike traditional robots, soft robots have structures that allow them to adapt to and interact with complex and dynamic environments. In consideration of their flexibility and adaptability, soft robots are versatile and can be designed for a wide range of applications, from medical devices to search and rescue operations. Their adaptability allows them to perform multiple tasks without the need for extensive reprogramming.

The Challenges

In the context of soft robotics, self-healing structural components represent an innovative feature that enhances the durability and reliability of the robots. Self-healing materials have the ability to repair damage autonomously, mitigating the impact of wear and tear. The current field is driven by the adoption of soft grippers that ensure safe operation for collaborative robots in manufacturing and delicate manipulation in agrifood and warehousing. However, these expensive and mostly non-recyclable soft robots have limited lifetimes due to their vulnerability.

Keywords:

#standardisation, #selfhealingmaterial, #softrobotics, #flexibleelectronics, #ISO, #CEN, #ecodesign, #greentransition

SHINTO: Mapping Standards in the Realm of Self-healing Properties.

The project

SHINTO – short name for **Self-Healing soft materials for sustainable products** – is a project aiming to disrupt the soft robotics market by creating a new market for self-healing structural components, introducing autonomous damage detection and healing in intelligent soft robots. In symbiosis, VUB-research groups FYSC and Brubotics have been building soft robots out of self-healing materials that fully recover functional material properties and resulting performances after healing incurred damage. This extends the robots service lifetime and raises their reliability and sustainability, which in combination with their inherent recyclability contributes to economic benefits and the EU Green Deal.

SHINTO REPRESENTATIVE

Joost Brancart

Postdoctoral Researcher at Vrije Universiteit Brussel

“Together with the HSbooster.eu consultant, the SHINTO consortium has set up an action plan for putting together a proposal for a new international standard.”

The Project Standardisation Needs

SHINTO applied to the standardisation booster service to get support in connecting the SHINTO management and researchers with the right stakeholders in the standardisation scene (standardisation organisations, technical committees, peer experts). The objective of the project was to gain insights into and investigate the standardisation landscape (relevant existing standards) in the new field of technology, assist the standardisation organisation to evaluate the need for new standards.

Keywords:

#standardisation, #selfhealingmaterial, #softrobotics, #flexibleelectronics, #ISO, #CEN, #ecodesign, #greentransition

SHINTO: Mapping Standards in the Realm of Self-healing Properties.

The HSbooster.eu Expert

Valter Loll is an active private consultant (Loll-Consult). He received his degree in Mechanical Engineering from The Danish Technical University in 1973 and a degree in business administration from the University of Kolding in 1979. Valter Loll worked for Nokia Mobile Phones as "Scientist, Quality and Reliability development" and taught business administration at the University of Aarhus. Since 1988 he has been active in the IEC TC56 standardisation committee and was the chairman of TC56, Dependability from 2008 until 2017. Of the 60 international standards in IEC TC56, Valter Loll was author or co-author on 15. Most of the 60 standards are also European Norms (EN) through parallel vote. Valter Loll is convener for the update of IEC 62506 Accelerated testing and expert member of 9 project teams. He is also chairman of the Shadow committee S-556 in Danish Standards.

THE HSBOOSTER.EU EXPERT

Valter Loll

Consultant and Chairman of the shadow committee S-556 under Danish Standards.

"International standardisation is slow and complicated, therefore it needs hands-on experience. I contributed to enabling a faster introduction of new methods."

The HSbooster.eu Consultancy service

After the identification of the challenges, i.e., standardisation of self-healing properties (mechanical aspects) and material reuse properties, the expert provided an overview of the standardisation process, covering terminology, data sheet declaration, test methods, samples, and management. The relevant standardisation bodies, ISO (international) and CEN (European), were identified. In particular, ISO Technical Committees - ISO/TC61 is relevant to SHINTO. SHINTO consortium representative presented the concept of "self-healing," addressing important issues for standardisation. Together with the expert, the SHINTO consortium representatives defined "self-healing" terminology and how to write a draft standard (WD). An official ISO definition is required. The planned standard will have to define "self-healing" in polymers. The stages in making a standard were discussed: Preliminary, Proposal, Preparatory, Committee Draft, Enquiry, and Approval. The expert explained how to write a WD and fill in all the necessary clauses. He also recommended to propose a Standard on Self-Healing Polymers.

SHINTO also checks if Belgium has a shadow committee for ISO/SC61, contacts the chairman of ISO/TC61 for relevant information. The next steps would be to inquire about presenting the proposed standard to the next plenary of ISO/TC61 as well as request the Belgium National Committee to put forward the new Work Item Proposal (NWIP).

Keywords:

#standardisation, #selfhealingmaterial, #softrobotics, #flexibleelectronics, #ISO, #CEN, #ecodesign, #greentransition

SHINTO: Mapping Standards in the Realm of Self-healing Properties.

Benefits & Impact

SHINTO's relevance in the standardisation landscape, particularly in the realm of self-healing properties, took centre stage during the delivery of the consultancy services provided by HSbooster.eu. The narrative pivoted to the quest for defining "self-healing" in polymers, an effort accompanied by a deep dive into ISO-specific rules and terminology. The service included an evaluation of the project readiness, mapping the standardisation landscape, and the engagement with relevant committees. A roadmap was defined together with a standardisation expert, involving the use of standards in new R&D proposals and actively proposing new work items. The final report of the services painted a picture of satisfaction and commitment. The SHINTO project expressed not just a commitment but an eagerness to follow expert suggestions for future strategies, leaving the door open for future consultations on standardisation.

Useful material

- [Self-Healing Soft Robots](#)

Future Plans

With the closure of the service, the focus now shifts to the implementation of expert recommendations, a blueprint for a future where innovation and standardisation walk hand in hand.

The expert suggested that SHINTO consortium representatives checked if Belgium had a shadow committee for ISO/SC61 and that they wrote a draft for the proposed standard. He also recommended to contact the chairman of ISO/TC61, ask for the name of the convener of ISO/TC61/SC2/WG7, and if possible participate at the plenary to present the proposed standard.

The HSbooster.eu service provided via Mr. Valter Loll, taught the researchers and business developers of the SHINTO project about the fundamentals of international standardisation, the international standard landscape relevant to the developed technology and advised the consortium regarding the process of developing a new standard.

Keywords:

#standardisation, #circulareconomy,
#criticalrawmaterials, #ashes, #Industry,
#urban, #symbiosis, #environment,
#sequestration

Influencing the Existing Standardisation Landscape through CEN Workshop Agreements.

Background

Ashes from the incineration of municipal solid waste, biomass and sewage sludge are currently underutilised and a part of them ends up in landfills. With them, a significant number of metals, nutrients, rare earth elements and industrially valuable minerals contained in the ashes are lost as well. Moreover, landfilling of ash costs at least 100-500 euros per tonne, and the costs are only expected to increase in the future. In the transition to a climate-neutral economy, the social dimension of industrial transformation must not be forgotten, as energy industry and construction sector are an essential part of the EU's economic and industrial structure.

The Challenges

The European Commission has recognised the necessity to recover Critical Raw Materials not only from virgin materials, but as much as possible also from secondary sources. Secondary Raw Materials can be sources used instead of primary raw materials. SRMs can also be a source for CRMs, which are of high economic importance due to the eventual scarcity on the EU market or supply disruption. The EU thus wishes to promote the recycling of these materials, especially the recovery of CRMs, as part of the move toward a circular economy.

Keywords:

#standardisation, #circulareconomy,
#criticalrawmaterials, #ashes, #Industry,
#urban, #symbiosis, #environment,
#sequestration

Influencing the Existing Standardisation Landscape through CEN Workshop Agreements.

The project

AshCycle is a Research and Innovation Action funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe under grant agreement N°101058162. The AshCycle project provides tools for reducing the waste generation from the incineration of municipal solid waste (MSW), biomass, sewage sludge, or combinations of them by developing new utilization possibilities. The project deploys exemplary pilot solutions of the Industrial-Urban Symbiosis (I-US) concept by demonstrating novel recovery methods for valuable elements from the ashes. Furthermore, the aluminosilicate-rich minerals recovered from the ashes are piloted as a feedstock for companies across value chains to obtain products for construction and wastewater treatment leading to increased resource efficiency and circularity.

ASHCYCLE REPRESENTATIVE

**Vilma
Ducman**

Slovenian National Building and Civil Engineering Institute

"After the HSbooster.eu service, we have decided to participate in the CWA "Guidelines on Action Research for Large Scale Piloting" as it aligned with AshCycle's objectives."

The Project Standardisation Needs

AshCycle applied to HSbooster.eu to effectively influence changes to existing standards. As the European Union is strongly committing to the strengthening of the circular economy principles and business models, standardisation efforts have to be supportive, promote and facilitate the market uptake of circular sustainable solutions. The project asked for additional information useful to extending the current standards and developing new ones, as well as insights on how to influence processes and outcomes of standardisation processes.

Keywords:

#standardisation, #circulareconomy,
#criticalrawmaterials, #ashes, #Industry,
#urban, #symbiosis, #environment,
#sequestration

Influencing the Existing Standardisation Landscape through CEN Workshop Agreements.

The HSbooster.eu Expert

Dejana Milinkovic, the expert assigned by HSbooster.eu, played a pivotal role in supporting AshCycle's standardisation endeavours. She has been Director of the Business Association of the Cement Industry of Serbia since 2010 and an active contributor in the national Technical Committees for the adoption of Serbian standards (as a Chairman of the TC for Cement and building lime - corresponding to CEN/TC 51) and a member of the TC for concrete - corresponding to CEN/TC 104). She has been involved in the work of CEN/TC 343, and since 2012, she has chaired the Assembly of the Institute for Standardisation of Serbia, until the end of 2021.

The HSbooster.eu Consultancy service

The assigned HSbooster.eu expert recognised the value of AshCycle's methodology and exploitation objectives. She provided valuable insights and guidance to the project team, facilitating their engagement with relevant standardisation activities and committees. AshCycle focused on reducing waste from incineration and developing innovative uses for ashes, which required guidance on extending current standards and potentially creating new ones. The consultancy service aimed to provide additional information crucial for the evolution of existing standards and offer insights on influencing standardization processes and outcomes.

This aligns with the project's goal to develop a roadmap for testing and positioning innovative solutions in the market, emphasizing adherence to CEN standards.

The expert suggested relevant committees to propose and contact for the extension of existing European standards or the development of Technical Specifications, notably CEN/TC 104 - Concrete and related products, CEN/TC 51 - Cement and building limes, an CEN/TC 227 - Road materials. The expert also recommended to assess the development of CEN Workshop Agreements and to familiarise with the document: CEN-CENELEC Guide 29 "CEN/ CENELEC Workshop Agreements—A rapid way to standardization.

The expert has also encouraged the project partners to get familiar with the HSbooster.eu resources, including the training academy - advanced level modules.

THE HSBOOSTER.EU EXPERT

**Dejana
Milinkovic**

Director at The Association of the Cement Industry of Serbia

"Quote."

Keywords:

#standardisation, #circulareconomy,
#criticalrawmaterials, #ashes, #Industry,
#urban, #symbiosis, #environment,
#sequestration

Influencing the Existing Standardisation Landscape through CEN Workshop Agreements.

Benefits & Impact

The support provided by Dejana and HSbooster.eu has brought benefits for AshCycle. The project gained a deeper understanding of standardisation practices and opportunities in the field of circularity in the construction industry. By engaging with the consultancy service, the project gained access to valuable information on influencing standardisation processes, ensuring that its innovative solutions align with existing standards and garner broader acceptance. This not only facilitates the market positioning of the developed products but also supports the goal of decreasing waste generation and CO2 emissions. The potential extension of existing European standards and participation in relevant Technical Committees has enhanced the sustainability performance of AshCycle's technologies. Through the HSbooster.eu service, AshCycle stands to make a significant impact on standardisation, contributing to the creation of new circular value chains in the EU.

Useful material

- [Literature review of material recovery technologies](#)
- [AshCycle - Presentation](#)

Future Plans

Based on the insights and recommendations provided by Dejana, AshCycle has a clear strategy for the future. The project is poised to contact relevant national mirror committees to propose and support the development of CEN/CENELEC Workshop Agreements (CWAs), following the rapid standardisation approach outlined in CEN-CENELEC Guide 29. Additionally, AshCycle plans to explore advanced-level training through HSbooster.eu Training Academy, particularly focusing on unlocking new value in urban waste.

The project is considering to assess and potentially support membership in CEN/TC 350/SC 1 - Circular Economy in the Construction Sector. This shows a commitment to aligning its innovations with circular economy principles.

The forthcoming actions, such as preparing CEN/CENELEC Workshop proposal forms and contacting relevant national mirror committees will be important milestones in the AshCycle's pathway towards standardisation, sustainability, and the circular economy.

Keywords:

#standardisation, #digitaltwins,
#mathematics, #modelling, #simulation,
#optimisation, #acoustics

Reduced Order Modelling, Simulation and Optimization of Coupled Systems

The project standardisation needs

ROMSOC's subproject ESR2 is focused on designing, implementing, and deploying accurate digital twins of any process of interest to achieve the best performance of mathematical modelling, simulation, and optimisation techniques. The objectives of this research project are the mathematical modelling and numerical simulation of acoustic coupled systems. The numerical results will play a key role in designing novel windscreens to mitigate the flow effects on the measures of acoustic probes.

The project identified three specific needs: A) how to use standardisation procedures for any stage regarding digital twins in non-destructive frameworks, B) how to transform the classical standards focused on real-world measurements into a digital twin scenario, and C) how to certify the digital twin predictions of non-destructive testings using standardisation. ROMSOC Consortium applied for the Standardisation Booster service to get valuable guidance in achieving these three goals.

THE HSBOOSTER.EU EXPERT

Muslim Elkotob

Principal Solutions Architect, Vodafone; Senior Expert at ETSI, ITU-T, IEEE, TMForum, BBF & other SDOs

"It was a pleasure – but also a challenge – to serve on ROMSOC. I delivered a lot and even learned a few things myself; the platform is very good and the team is excellent."

PROJECT REPRESENTATIVE

Andrés Prieto

Associate professor, Department of Mathematics (University of A Coruña), researcher in CITMAga

"The training academy is a great source of information, the expert choice was adequate and the curated material on the web is very helpful."

The HSbooster.eu Consultancy service

ROMSOC's subproject ESR2 deals with mathematical modelling and numerical simulation of coupled porous multilayer systems for enabling particle velocity measurements in the presence of airflow. The core objectives of the HSbooster.eu consulting service include the analysis of the standardisation potential and perspectives of the work done in ESR2 on developing a digital twin of an acoustic device, to recommend a set of further potentially relevant standards to look at (in the areas of Digital Twins and Device Simulation), and to provide a high-level description of important steps for successfully standardising work in the Digital Twins area.

The service was a first step to set the frame for connecting the work done in ROMSOC ESR-2 to the world of standards and standardisation. If the developed acoustic device model is successfully aligned to standards, and the new parts are then set as new standards for the industry, this would be a trendsetter for further similar developments.

Keywords:

#standardisation, #5G, #QoE, #digitalisation,
#internet, #data, #networks, #testbed

5G Applications and Devices Benchmarking

The project standardisation needs

The **TRIANGLE Project** has refined its findings to create a focused framework that captured the interest of ITU-T Q17/12, leading to the Y.TestBed standardisation initiative. This initiative presented a structured testbed setup and methodology to evaluate the Quality of Experience (QoE) of multiple 5G and beyond mobile use cases. The Y.TestBed Recommendation offered a calibrated, automated testbed and testing methodology designed to deliver consistent, repeatable results using commercial devices and applications, aiming at making results more valuable by mimicking the setup of a real user.

TRIANGLE's team has launched the Y.TestBed work item within ITU-T SG12 (Q17/12), but it faced challenges due to limited experience in standard writing. Through HSbooster, TRIANGLE aimed to receive expert feedback and guidance to ensure their contributions meet ITU-T standards and build the team's expertise in standardisation for future initiatives.

THE HSBOOSTER.EU EXPERT

Pankaj Pandey

Research Scientist at the Norwegian University of Science and Technology; Founder & Techno-Commercial Manager at Pandey Techsolutions; Expert at ISO, ECSO, ISACA and EC.

"TRIANGLE project's efforts to pioneer 5G QoE standards are impressive, and guiding their ITU pathway under HSB was truly a privilege."

PROJECT REPRESENTATIVE

Mattia Lecci

R&D Researcher at Keysight Technologies

"HSB was crucial during the final stages of our standardisation process. Having expert insights helped us ensure appropriate language, identify potential logical issues, and fully prepare for the SDO meeting."

The HSbooster.eu Consultancy service

The project focused on the Draft Recommendation ITU-T Y.TestBed, which proposed a test bed framework for evaluating mobile application QoS and QoE, developed under ITU-T Study Group 12, Q17-TD002. To support the project's progress, the HSB expert provided targeted guidance on the editorial refinement of the draft recommendation and on navigating the ITU approval process. Following the expert's advice, the project team successfully presented at the ITU SG2 meeting in February 2024, where the draft recommendation was discussed.

Post-meeting, the expert reviewed further edits and provided detailed feedback, leading to a final meeting focused on aligning the draft for ITU's next stages. Additionally, the expert advised engaging with key standardisation committees and SDOs (e.g., ISO, IEC, IEEE), and outlined strategies to advance the draft recommendation. Final preparations were underway for submitting the draft to Study Group members.

Keywords:

#standardisation, #CBRN, #Microscopy,
#Aerosol, #Pathogens, #CivilSecurity

Increasing bio-aerosol sensing/ measurement capability of CBRN practitioners.

The project standardisation needs

HoloZcan is an innovative initiative focusing on enhancing societal resilience against Chemical, Biological, Radiological, and Nuclear (CBRN) incidents. This project is primarily centered around the development of an autonomous biodetection device, employing advanced technology to detect and analyze potential CBRN threats. Digital Holographic Microscopy Combined with Fluorescence Microscopy: The project demonstrates the application of this novel technology in civil security, particularly in field measurements. This technology is a significant advancement in detecting and analyzing microscopic particles and organisms in various environments.

HoloZcan aims to find connections with ongoing standardisation processes in this field and contribute to the development of missing standards.

PROJECT REPRESENTATIVE

**Györgyi
Bela**

Senior Researcher at IDEAS Science &
HoloZcan coordinator

"We have had the privilege of working with a dedicated expert who has shown exceptional professionalism, extensive experience and a vast network in the security field, particularly in the CBRN area."

The HSbooster.eu Consultancy service

The assigned HSbooster.eu expert shared insights on which SDOs to engage with and provided advice on how to influence processes and outcomes of standardisation. She suggested how to propose new standardisation items to a Technical Committee and advised on questions for preparatory work before the final decision-making. The expert leveraged her network to support the project in engaging with relevant Technical Committees and Working Groups, such as CEN/TC 391 Societal and Citizen Security WG2 – High-Risk Hazards & CBRNE, among others. Over the meetings with the the project representatives, the expert presented the scenario of Relevant Standard Operational Procedures (SOPs) and Methods for Proficiency Interlaboratory testing schemes, the case of valorisation of Interlaboratory comparisons (ILCs). Thanks to the work carried out, the project is expected to be presented in relevant Technical Committees and Working Groups as well as potentially contribute to the on-going standardisation projects within them.

THE HSBOOSTER.EU EXPERT

**Aikaterini
Poustourli**

Scientific/Technical Officer at the
International Hellenic University

"Strengthening the sensing/measurement capability of CBRN practitioners and preparedness for CBRN risks ultimately is strengthening the EU's Resilience against CBRN threats. HoloZcan's outcomes and future consortium involvement in standardisation activities will be key in this domain."

Keywords:

#standardisation, #antimicrobialresistance, #AMR, #animalhealth, #health, #medicine, #veterinary, #microbiology, #foodchain

AVANT – Alternatives to Veterinary ANTimicrobials

The project standardisation needs

AVANT addressed the human health risk posed by excessive antimicrobial use in veterinary medicine due to the potential transfer of resistant bacteria. Focused on managing pig enteritis, a leading reason for antimicrobial use in food animals, AVANT explored various solutions, including gut microbiome modulators, innovative medicines targeting pathogens or enhancing the pig's immune response, and feed-based preventive strategies. After pre-clinical studies that considered regulatory aspects, the most promising interventions were tested in farm trials. Mathematical modelling also played a key role in predicting how these alternatives could reduce antimicrobial use.

AVANT sought guidance on leveraging project data and findings to support and influence the development of new standards in animal health. These standards aimed to promote effective and sustainable veterinary practices in antimicrobial use.

PROJECT REPRESENTATIVE

Luca Guardabassi

Professor in One Health AMR, University of Copenhagen

"HSB has been a valuable tool for generating feedback and developing potential activities for the dissemination and future exploitation of project results, whether by establishing new standards or contributing to existing ones."

The HSbooster.eu Consultancy service

During the initial call, the HSbooster.eu expert provided targeted advice on navigating the standardisation landscape, including initial recommendations on TCs relevant to animal health, databases for finding appropriate standards, and a strategic approach to integrating standardisation within the project. Preliminary suggestions included

- liaison with CEN/TC 469 "Animal health diagnostic analyses";
- alignment with the cluster project ArMoR to broaden the impact of AVANT's findings.

The project was encouraged to proactively engage with identified standardisation committees and align project results with standardisation frameworks for potential uptake. The expert recommended preparing to launch a CWA about six months before the project ends to ensure thorough integration. Continuous, constructive exchanges with the expert were beneficial and raised awareness of standardisation, yet additional partner engagement was needed to fully realise AVANT's standardisation objectives.

THE HSBOOSTER.EU EXPERT

René Lindner

Freelance consultant for standardisation in research projects. (Formerly: Tecnun – University of Navarra, DIN German Institute for Standardisation)

"I identified key standardisation committees and guided the approach, helping the project find additional committees of interest. By highlighting the benefits, I enabled smoother integration into future proposals."

Keywords:
#standardisation, #5G, #6G,
#telecommunications, #landscape, #tracker,
#snsju

6G SNS OPS

SNS OPS – Building a Standardisation Tracker for 6G

The project standardisation needs

The **SNS OPS** project supports the operations of the SNS Joint Undertaking (JU), facilitating the European SNS Initiative as outlined in its contractual partnership. Its work focuses on coordinating Smart Networks and Services (SNS) projects, aligning them with the 6G Infrastructure Association and EU strategic policies. Key activities include fostering collaboration across projects on critical issues like standardisation and spectrum, promoting European leadership in 6G, and ensuring impactful exploitation of SNS results. Additionally, the project organises strategic actions to capture the European perspective on 6G advancements, monitor their impact, and plan for future efforts to sustain Europe's momentum and leadership in the global 6G landscape.

SNS OPS sought guidance to gather inputs and restructure the Standards Tracker platform. This platform helps stakeholders navigate the evolving landscape, through reports profiling stakeholder engagement across sectors, roles, and regions.

THE HSBOOSTER.EU EXPERT

Muslim Elkotob

Principal Solutions Architect at Vodafone

"My goal with SNS-OPS was to make research results and the standards landscape more searchable, parametrized, and accessible, ensuring the industry and R&D community can fully engage and benefit."

PROJECT REPRESENTATIVE

Claudio de Majo

Senior Research Analyst at Trust-IT Services

"The HSbooster.eu free consultancy service has played a key role in reshaping and improving this useful tool, which will gain a lot of visibility across the SNS JU community in the next few months."

The HSbooster.eu Consultancy service

Through Muslim's consultancy, the SNS OPS project has significantly upgraded its **Standards Tracker platform**, moving from a basic, flat-structured system to a sophisticated, multi-dimensional database designed to better serve researchers, industry professionals, and policymakers. The platform now incorporates six filters—use case/application type, technology tier, technology paradigm, research contribution type, standards landscape, and optional verticals—providing a robust framework for classifying, locating, and retrieving content with high precision. This transformation enhances users' ability to navigate and utilise the tool's library of R&D outputs and standards, fostering greater knowledge sharing and collaboration. Starting with 20 parameterised standards in Phase I, the project has expanded to 120 high-quality entries in Phase II, covering prominent SDOs. The new system enables targeted searches based on specific criteria, including technology tiers, paradigms, and application types, ensuring relevance and utility across diverse research and industrial needs.

Keywords:

#standardisation, #FCHtechnologies,
#hydrogen, #recycling, #sustainable design,
#ISO, #IEC

BEST4Hy – Pioneering Standards for Hydrogen Fuel Cell Recycling

The project standardisation needs

BEST4Hy, a project focused on developing and validating recycling techniques for hydrogen fuel cell technologies, identified a pressing need to align its innovations with existing and emerging standards. The project sought guidance to address the lack of comprehensive standards for managing the end-of-life phase of fuel cells, specifically PEMFC and SOFC technologies.

With the aim of integrating sustainable design, disassembly, and handling of end-of-life fuel cell components, BEST4Hy needed support to identify relevant standards and benchmark its methods against approaches used in similar fields, such as those involving precious and hazardous materials. The project also required insights into technical committees and directives, such as IEC TC105 (Fuel Cell Technologies), IEC TC111 (Environmental Standardisation), and ISO TC197 (Hydrogen Technologies), to ensure its findings would contribute meaningfully to standardisation efforts.

THE HSBOOSTER.EU EXPERT

Seyed Mohammad Mousavi Agah

Principal Power System Studies Engineer at RPG Power Systems

"It was a privilege to contribute to BEST4Hy by ensuring its standardisation requirements were met, providing a solid foundation for consistency and quality. I'm truly glad to have supported the team in achieving this critical milestone for project success."

PROJECT REPRESENTATIVE

Ilaria Schiavi

Project Manager & Business Development Exec at Environment Park

"Standardisation is key to support the progress of innovation, and thus the help of HSBooster has been fundamental. HSB has helped BEST4Hy in identifying the relevant standard committee where the progress of the innovation developed could be better supported"

The HSbooster.eu Consultancy service

HSbooster.eu provided BEST4Hy with strategic advice to navigate the underdeveloped standardisation landscape in hydrogen recycling. The service included a comprehensive mapping of relevant standards and technical committees, identifying gaps in the current framework and opportunities for engagement. Experts recommended participation in national mirror committees, particularly in Italy, to align the project with ongoing discussions in IEC TC105, IEC TC111, and ISO TC197.

The consultancy also advised on engaging with directives such as WEEE and Eco-design, highlighting their relevance to fuel cell recycling. Tailored recommendations were provided to help the consortium propose a new working group dedicated to the end-of-life management of fuel cell technologies, using their research to shape emerging standards.

Keywords:
#standardisation, #NatureBasedSolutions,
#NbS, #CEN, #ISO, #sustainability

NetworkNature – Advancing Standards for Nature-Based Solutions

The project standardisation needs

NetworkNature recognised a critical need to integrate Nature-Based Solutions (NbS) into the standardisation landscape to ensure broader recognition, impact, and adoption. As a platform encompassing over 80 European projects across diverse topics—including under others NbS in cities, coastal areas, and wetlands—NetworkNature identified raising awareness of standardisation among its Task Forces as the most effective way to generate momentum. Engaging HSBooster experts was pivotal in achieving this objective, helping to map the challenges, risks, and priorities associated with NbS implementation. Understanding the standards landscape was crucial for aligning the project's outcomes with relevant standards and creating pathways for meaningful contributions. NetworkNature sought strategic guidance to engage with standardisation bodies, foster collaboration between Task Forces and technical committees, and explore the potential for a CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA) to accelerate the standardisation of outputs generated by its five Task Forces. These efforts aimed to address practical challenges such as ensuring data reliability, quantifying the economic value of NbS benefits, and promoting inclusive governance models.

THE HSBOOSTER.EU EXPERT

Dr. René Lindner

Freelance consultant for standardisation in research projects (formerly: Tecnun - University of Navarra, DIN German Institute for Standardization)

"Compared to advising a single project, the support for NetworkNature also made it possible to get a further 20 projects interested in standardisation, even though they all had very different levels of knowledge and interests. That was simply great fun."

THE HSBOOSTER.EU EXPERT

Dr. Diana Soeiro

Portuguese Business Ethics Association (APEE), Expert and Delegate at ISO/TC 268 and CEN/TC 465

"What I found most rewarding was advocating for greater diversity in stakeholders and emphasising the need for broader involvement of European countries to ensure standardisation addresses everyone's needs."

PROJECT REPRESENTATIVE

Daniela Rizzi, PhD

Senior Expert for Nature-based Solutions and Biodiversity NetworkNature coordinator

"The collaboration between NetworkNature and HS Booster has been instrumental in fostering interest and engagement in standardization across the more than 80 EU-funded projects on Nature-based Solutions. The NetworkNature-led Task Force workshop in Brussels in the Summer of 2024, supported by UNI, was a resounding success, demonstrating standards' critical role in advancing and scaling NbS. As a result, we see increased interest in the projects to launch their own CEN Workshop Agreements (CWA), accelerating and strengthening the impact of nature-based solutions across Europe."

The HSbooster.eu Consultancy service

HSbooster.eu provided both strategic and practical support to enable NetworkNature's effective engagement within the standardisation ecosystem. Through a formal liaison with CEN/TC 465, the project established direct communication channels with the relevant technical committees. The service consisted in three main steps:

- **Awareness raising:** a series of workshops equipped NetworkNature's Task Forces with knowledge about standardisation processes
- **Identification of standardisation potential:** HSB highlighted opportunities for contributing to standards development.
- **Preparation for standardisation activities:** HSB supported the initiation of a CWA, funding its development and facilitating expert advice from UNI representatives to ensure alignment with European and international frameworks.

The outputs from this collaboration will now significantly shape contributions to the emerging standards landscape enhancing NetworkNature's overall impact.

Keywords:
#standardisation, #CCAM, #ITS,
#connectedvehicles, #ISO

SELFY – Pioneering Resilience and Security in CCAM through Standards and Interoperability

The project standardisation needs

SELFY addresses the critical challenges of ensuring resilience and cybersecurity in Cooperative, Connected, and Automated Mobility (CCAM). By developing a comprehensive toolbox of collaborative solutions, SELFY seeks to enhance CCAM resilience, secure data privacy, and enable seamless data sharing across platforms and borders. Recognising the need for interoperability and standardisation to achieve its objectives, SELFY identified gaps in existing frameworks and sought guidance on navigating the complex standardisation landscape.

The project's key challenges include establishing secure communication mechanisms, aligning with global standards, and fostering collaboration across diverse stakeholders. These challenges are compounded by the need for robust cybersecurity measures to protect against evolving threats, ensuring both the safety and trustworthiness of CCAM ecosystems.

PROJECT REPRESENTATIVE

David Fidalgo

Founder & CEO at Y-Mobility

"HSbooster and its expert team provided invaluable guidance, helping us navigate the process of engaging with standardisation committees and understanding how to integrate these efforts within our organisation."

The HSbooster.eu Consultancy service

The service facilitated SELFY's engagement with ISO TC204/WG17 on Intelligent Transport Systems, identified as the most relevant technical committee for its work. Through this engagement, SELFY participated in workshops and plenaries, including an ISO annual meeting where its use cases and project results were presented by AEVAC, the Spanish Association for Connected Autonomous Vehicles. This opportunity allowed the project to gain valuable feedback from international experts and refine its contributions.

In addition, HSbooster guided SELFY in initiating steps to join ISO through UNE, granting strategic access to standards and resources critical to its long-term objectives. This comprehensive support ensured that SELFY could effectively navigate the complex world of standardisation while maximising its impact.

THE HSBOOSTER.EU EXPERT

Eusebiu Catana

Research and Innovation Consultant at ERTICO

"I believe robust standards are the foundation of innovation. My role with SELFY was to guide them in navigating standardisation confidently and ensuring their contributions make a lasting impact."

Keywords:

#health, #data, #standardisation,
#interoperability, #AI, #healthinformatics,
#HL7FHIR, #EHDS

IDERHA and the Health Cluster – Advancing Health Data Standardisation

The project standardisation needs

The **IDERHA project**, in collaboration with **ASCAPE, iHELP, Bigpicture, EUCAIM, and HealthData@EU**, formed a health project cluster to address shared standardisation challenges in health data. The cluster focused on harmonising data models, ontologies, and terminologies using key health standards such as HL7 FHIR, DICOM, OMOP, and ISO TC 215 Health Informatics. Their goal was to ensure interoperability and seamless data sharing across borders, particularly for cancer-related use cases.

These efforts culminated in the publication of the paper “Synergies Among Health Data Projects with Cancer Use Cases Based on Health Standards” at the MIE 2024 conference. Additionally, the cluster is working on a European Health Data Space (EHDS) interoperability framework, aiming to facilitate cohesive data exchange and alignment with EU health policies.

THE HSBOOSTER.EU EXPERT

Amélie Gyrard

Research and Innovation Consultant at Trialog

“HSBooster.eu provided a networking opportunity among European Health Data Projects working on cancer use cases, focusing on health standards to enhance semantic interoperability. Our amazing collaboration led to scientific publications.”

PROJECT REPRESENTATIVE

Rada Hussein

Health Informatics Expert, Principal Investigator
at Ludwig Boltzmann Institute for Digital Health and
Prevention

“With the HSbooster support, the IDERHA team explored the existing semantic standards and future AI standards shaping EHDS. Collaboratively, we consolidated the lessons learned into the EHDS2 interoperability framework toolkit to share the cluster expertise with future projects.”

The HSbooster.eu Consultancy service

HSbooster.eu provided critical support to the IDERHA project and the health cluster through:

- One-to-One Consultancy: Tailored guidance to assess standardisation readiness and align with health data standards.
- Collaboration Enablement: Facilitating the formation of the health cluster to pool expertise and create synergies.
- Deep-Dive Workshop: Participation in HSbooster webinars on AI standardisation, to disseminate the cluster’s findings and engage stakeholders.
- Development of the EHDS Interoperability Framework: Supporting the creation of the European Health Data Space (EHDS) interoperability framework

These activities empowered the cluster to develop a joint standardisation strategy, produce impactful publications, and advance the EHDS interoperability framework, demonstrating the value of collaborative approaches in health data standardisation.

Keywords:
#standardisation, #green, #hydrogen,
#sustainability, #CEN, #ISO,
#energytransition

 H₂ VALUE

H2Value – Shaping Standards for Green Hydrogen Implementation

The project standardisation needs

H2Value, a project committed to advancing green hydrogen technologies, sought expert guidance to navigate the complexities of standardisation and align its activities with relevant European and international frameworks. The project faced challenges such as the lack of comprehensive safety and security guidelines, administrative barriers in permitting processes, and technical uncertainties in integrating hydrogen into existing systems, including gas networks.

To address these issues, H2Value needed a clearer understanding of the current state of green hydrogen standards and policies, particularly at the EU level, and support in identifying opportunities to influence standardisation outcomes. Additionally, the project aimed to equip its stakeholders, including city officials and local partners in Estonia and Lithuania, with the knowledge and tools to engage effectively with standardisation bodies and integrate best practices across the hydrogen value chain.

THE HSBOOSTER.EU EXPERT

Paola Amato

Architect and Standardisation Expert

"H2Value demonstrates how experimental applications of green hydrogen technologies across the value chain can contribute to identifying new standards while enhancing market prospects for advanced European solutions."

PROJECT REPRESENTATIVE

Aivars Starikovs

Member Board of Directors at Hydrogen Europe

The HSbooster.eu Consultancy service

HSbooster.eu delivered a comprehensive consultancy service, beginning with an analysis of the green hydrogen standards landscape and highlighting key gaps and emerging priorities. This included insights into technical committees such as ISO/TC 197 on Hydrogen Technologies and CEN/CLC/JTC 6 on Hydrogen in Energy Systems, which were identified as relevant to the project's goals.

The consultancy also helped H2Value refine its internal processes by mapping where standardisation could enhance risk management and operational planning.

Tailored recommendations were provided to strengthen the project's ability to contribute to evolving standards, supported by targeted training opportunities through the HSbooster Academy. These training sessions focused on building capacity among city officials and stakeholders to navigate the complexities of hydrogen safety, permitting, and system integration.

Keywords:

#standardisation, #hydrogen, #ammonia,
#cleanenergy, #ISO, #CEN

SINGLE – Setting the Standard for Ammonia in the Hydrogen Value Chain

The project standardisation needs

SINGLE is a pioneering project focused on exploring ammonia's role within the hydrogen value chain, addressing its potential as a carrier in clean energy systems. As a highly experimental initiative, SINGLE required guidance on navigating the complex and evolving standardisation landscape for hydrogen and ammonia technologies.

The project aimed to establish a strategic approach to standardisation, ensuring its outcomes could inform and align with emerging standards. Specific objectives included identifying relevant standards for ammonia and hydrogen, mapping the EU legislative framework, and engaging with key technical committees such as ISO/TC 197 (Hydrogen Technologies) and CEN/CLC/JTC 6 (Hydrogen in Energy Systems). SINGLE also sought support to collaborate with other experimental projects, leveraging lessons learned to refine its approach and contribute to new or revised standards.

THE HSBOOSTER.EU EXPERT

Paola Amato

Architect and Standardisation Expert

"SINGLE well demonstrates how development of highly experimental technologies needs acquiring knowledge over complex and evolving standardisation policies promoted by the EC."

PROJECT REPRESENTATIVE

Ruth Moya

Project Engineer at Gécrio

"HSBooster provided invaluable guidance at the start of our project, offering insights into regulations, regulatory committees, and relevant standards. Their support helped us craft a detailed plan of standardisation activities, ensuring alignment with existing standards and preparation for those critical to deploying and implementing our project outcomes."

The HSbooster.eu Consultancy service

HSbooster.eu provided critical support to SINGLE, starting with the development of Deliverable 7.4, a comprehensive plan for standardisation activities. The consultancy offered expert guidance on structuring the deliverable and provided resources to deepen the project's understanding of the EU legal framework and standardisation processes. This foundational work ensured a strong basis for the project's ongoing engagement with standardisation organisations. To address the project's needs, HSbooster facilitated the identification of relevant standards and technical committees, highlighting areas where SINGLE could make impactful contributions. Recommendations included strategic actions for engaging with ISO/TC 197 and CEN/CLC/JTC 6, as well as opportunities to propose new standards related to ammonia as part of the hydrogen value chain. The expert also identified training opportunities through the HSbooster Academy, helping project partners enhance their knowledge of standards and their role in clean energy transitions.

Keywords:

#standardisation, #fintech, #AI,
#blockchain, #dataspaces, #ISO, #W3C

INFINITECH and FAME – Standardisation in Financial and Insurance Technologies

The project standardisation needs

INFINITECH and its successor project, FAME, recognised the importance of standardisation to ensure interoperability, security, and scalability within financial and insurance technologies. INFINITECH, focusing on areas such as blockchain, privacy, and AI-powered solutions, required support to validate its progress and align its innovations with existing standards. As the project was in its later stages, there was a need to identify relevant standardisation opportunities and effectively communicate results to technical committees and stakeholders.

FAME expanded upon INFINITECH's achievements, aiming to establish a federated, secure, and energy-efficient data marketplace for embedded finance. This involved leveraging lessons from INFINITECH, such as its blockchain infrastructure, while introducing new features like DataOps and MLOps solutions. Standardisation support was needed to align these innovations with key standards in Artificial Intelligence, Decentralised Identifiers and Verifiable Credentials

THE HSBOOSTER.EU EXPERT

Marga Martin Sanchez

HSbooster.eu Expert and Deputy Director R&D at DEKRA

"Having the opportunity to guide the INFINITECH and FAME projects in engaging with standardisation organisations has been an enriching experience. This collaboration supported the development of de-facto standards and facilitated the alignment of their cutting-edge innovations with key international standards, ensuring interoperability, security, privacy, and scalability in the financial and insurance sectors"

PROJECT REPRESENTATIVE

Ilknur Chulani

Senior Programme Manager at
International Data Spaces Association

Support from HSBooster.eu was instrumental in taking our standardisation efforts to the next level in the FAME project. We received advice on which standardisation topics and which SDOs to consider, which was very helpful!

The HSbooster.eu Consultancy service

HSbooster.eu provided tailored guidance to INFINITECH and FAME, enabling both projects to effectively navigate the standardisation landscape and contribute meaningfully to relevant frameworks. For INFINITECH, HSbooster facilitated a successful liaison with ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27/WG 5 on Identity Management and Privacy Technologies, leading to contributions to ISO/IEC 27562: Privacy Guidelines for Fintech Services. Key inputs included privacy impact assessments and recommendations for traceability measures to enhance data security and anomaly detection. Additionally, INFINITECH's blockchain infrastructure, supporting ERC-1155 tokenisation, was recognised by IEEE and the Ethereum Forum, Building on this foundation, FAME received guidance on contributing to W3C's Financial Industry Business Ontology for embedded finance applications and participated in the CEN Workshop on Trusted Data Transactions.

Keywords:
#standardisation,
#materialscharacterisation,
#nanotechnology, #terminology, #metadata,

 nanoMECommons

NanoMECommons – Driving clarity in materials characterisation

The project standardisation needs

The **NanoMECommons project** addresses a critical need for consistency and clarity in materials characterisation and terminology. By leading the revision of CWA 17815:2021, NanoMECommons aims to create a unified framework for documenting characterisation experiments and data processing. The integration of the Characterisation Methodology Ontology (CHAMEO) into this revision will provide a machine-readable reference for terminology and metadata, enhancing the accessibility and utility of the standard across disciplines. The project aims to establish a standardised approach to data documentation, ensuring better interoperability, data sharing, and innovation, as well as transparency and market efficiency. Insights from NanoMECommons are shaping the updated CWA to reflect modern workflows and the needs of interdisciplinary communities.

PROJECT REPRESENTATIVE

Gerhard Goldbeck

Managing Director at Goldbeck Consulting and CWA Chair

“The strong engagement of many experts from different fields of materials science in the CWA has enabled us to extend the scope of the CHADA to a much wider range of cases, including test series and materials systems.”

The HSbooster.eu Consultancy service

HSbooster.eu provided tailored support to NanoMECommons, enabling impactful contributions to the revision of CWA 17815:2021, titled “Materials characterisation – Terminology, metadata, and classification”. Specifically, HSbooster.eu:

- Deployed two experts to support the workshop activities.
- Connected NanoMECommons with UNI, the Italian Standardisation Body, which acted as the workshop secretariat.
- Covered part of the secretariat fees to facilitate the workshop's operation and enhance the project's capacity to engage in standardisation.

The CWA, officially launched in May 2024, is focussing on creating a common language for materials characterisation and modelling, improving the documentation of experimental workflows and data processing and bridging the gap between research and industrial applications. The publication is expected in January 2025

THE HSBOOSTER.EU EXPERT

Raoul Schönhof

Manager at Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft

“Economic prosperity thrives on collaboration. Collaboration needs a common language. Standardisation is that language – and HSBooster empowers Europe to speak it fluently.”

THE HSBOOSTER.EU EXPERT

Karin Eufinger

Standardisation and Technical Regulations Manager, at Centexbel

“As a former researcher and now expert in standardisation I was very happy to provide support NanoMECommons to translate the results of their project into a CEN standardisation deliverable.”

THE NSB REPRESENTATIVE

Chiara Pia

Technical Officer at UNI

“The experts that participated in the CEN Workshop enriched the NanoMECommons project with their perspective. Sharing good practices and innovation from different fields is key to standardisation.”

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